

Analysis Prejudice And Destructive Behavior In Si Anak Badai Novel By Tere Liye by Novitasari

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is This study aims to describe 1) the prejudice of the characters toward the governor's delegation in Si Anak Badai novel by Tere Liye, 2) The impact of the character's prejudice on the governor's delegation in Si Anak Badai novel by Tere Liye. This research is a descriptive qualitative study with a literary psychology approach. The data source is the novel Si Anak Badai by Tere Liye. Data in the form of story units that are manifested in dialogues, paragraphs, and narratives that explain the character's prejudice about other characters. The data collection technique used the reading and notes technique and then grouped them in a table.

Keywords: *prejudice, destructive behavior, Si Anak Badai novel, literary psychology.*

INTRODUCTION

Novell'sNovell'se type of literary work that describes real human life with the addition of spices of imagination given by the author to add flavor and also become a separate strategy in attracting the general public's reading interest. In life, there must be various problems including friendship, love, resistance, individual dependence on other individuals, the dislike between individuals or groups, and much more. In a prejudice, there are motives of suspicion born of individual and group subjectivity towards other groups, most of which appear marked by a sense of superiority from the majority group who views the minority group as inferior.

The choice of the novel Si Anak Badai is the object of study because apart from being interesting to study in terms of prejudice and destructive behavior, the novel is the sixth book in Tere Liye's Children's Archipelago Series. This novel is about the lives of the country's children whose stories can be enjoyed by all people. This novel contains local wisdom that tells about life in Manowa village, a village where all activities, even houses, mosques, and schools are all on the water. Based on the search results, previous studies that examined the prejudice and destructive behavior of characters in the novel Si Anak Badai have not been found. With the above background, the differences and advantages of this study when compared to existing resealielies in the focus of this study on the prejudice and destructive behavior of the characters in Tere Liye's novel Si Anak Badai.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The theory used is the Ahmadi prejudice theory which breaks one's prejudices into three, namely cognitive and conative prejudices. The data of this research are in the form of story units that are realized in dialogues, paragraphs, and character narrations that describe the form of the character's prejudice against other characters and also the impacts that arise due to the character's prejudice.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions in this section, the results of the analysis of the character's prejudice against the governor's envoy who established the port without the agreement of the people of the Manowa village will be presented which is manifested in three types of prejudice which include cognitive, affective, and conative, as well as the impact that occurs as a result of these prejudices making the governor's envoy increasingly desperate for the smooth development of the port in the village of Manowar.

Cognitive prejudice is a prejudice that refers to what is considered true, such as perceptions and beliefs. In the novel *Si Anak Badai* by Tere Liye, there are two cognitive prejudices, namely perception, and belief. Perception is a process carried out by individuals to select, organize, and interpret information input to create a meaningful picture. Belief is an attitude shown by an individual when he feels he knows enough and concludes that he has reached the truth. As for the impact, of the construction of the port in Manowa village is continued, the cost of dredging the land requires quite a lot of money, also the economic scale of the construction will not be achieved because Manowa village is not yet in need of a large port. Destructive behavior tends to be carried out by those in power. so that people are powerless and submissive to the authorities.

CONCLUSION

How the writer subjectively species from the paper analysis that the description of the form of prejudice or prejudice against the governor's representative is not only in the form of an assumption that is true or not but also in the form of liking or disliking something, as well as actions to prove that the prejudice is true or not. The preconceived notions of these figures certainly had an impact on the

attitude and behavior of the governor's envoys (presumed people) who originally came with respect and courtesy, turned cruel and even desperate to launch a port development plan in Manowa Village. The destructive attitude carried out by the ruler leads to aggressive behavior and can also show power or hegemony in society.

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